

Scope & Topics

The International Journal of Chaos, Control, Modelling and Simulation is a Quarterly open access peer-reviewed journal that publishes articles which contribute new results in all areas of Chaos Theory, Control Systems, Scientific Modelling and Computer Simulation. In the last few decades, chaos theory has found important applications in secure communication devices and secure data encryption. Control methods are very useful in several applied areas like Chaos, Automation, Communication, Robotics, Power Systems, and Biomedical Instrumentation. The journal focuses on all technical and practical aspects of Chaos, Control, Modelling and Simulation. The goal of this journal is to bring together researchers and practitioners from academia and industry to focus on chaotic systems and applications, control theory, process control, automation, modelling concepts, computational methods, computer simulation and establishing new collaborations in these areas.

Areas and subareas of interest include (but are not limited to):

- Adaptive control
- Advanced chaos theory
- Advanced computing techniques
- Algorithms, modelling and simulation
- Applications of chaos in science and engineering
- Artificial intelligence
- Artificial neural networks
- Automation and mobile robots
- Bioinformatics
- Biological modelling
- Biological systems and models
- Chaotic systems
- Chaos modelling
- Circuit realization of chaotic systems
- Control of chaotic systems
- Cloud computing
- Communication engineering
- Computational biology
- Computational fluid dynamics
- Computer science
- Control devices & instruments
- Control theory
- Data mining
- Data Structures and Algorithms
- Scientific computing
- Secure communication devices
- Stochastic modelling and control
- Data visualization
- Digital control
- Digital image processing
- Digital signal processing
- Dynamical systems and stability theory
- Embedded systems and control
- Evolutionary techniques in engineering
- Flight control and surveillance systems
- Fuzzy logic control
- Genetic algorithms and applications
- Hyperchaotic systems
- Industrial applications of control
- Intelligent systems
- Information theory
- Linear and nonlinear programming
- Linear control theory
- Materials science
- Mathematical control theory
- Mathematical modelling and applications
- Measurement systems
- Modelling and control
- Nonlinear control theory
- Numerical methods in control systems
- Optimization and optimal control
- Parallel computing
- Process control and automation
- Real-time systems
- Real and complex analysis
- Robust control
- Soft computing technique

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers for this journal through **Email: ijccms@airconline.com** or through **[Submission System](#)**. Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this Journal. For paper format download the template in this page

Important Dates

- Submission Deadline : **August 01, 2023**
- Notification : September 01, 2023
- Final Manuscript Due : September 08, 2023
- Publication Date : Determined by the Editor-in-Chief

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